

Pant Dhan 6, a new variety for the hills of Uttar Pradesh

M. P. Pandey, S. C. Mani, H. Singh, J. P. Singh, S. Singh, and D. Singh, Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

The hilly region of Uttar Pradesh (about 46,485 km²) has diverse soil, topography, and rainfall. High-yielding varieties capable of performing well at lower and medium altitudes (up to 1,676 m) have been lacking.

Pant Dhan 6, a high-yielding variety recently released for this area, was evolved by the pedigree method following hybridization of IR8608-298-3-1 and IR10179-23 at IRRI. As IR19728-9-3-2, it was introduced in India through the 1981 International Rice Observational Nursery and grown at Pantnagar during the wet season.

Pant Dhan 6 is an early maturing (113-120 d in the hills), semidwarf variety suitable for transplanting at lower and medium altitudes. During 3 or testing, Pant Dhan 6 performed better than K39, Majhera 3, Thapachini, and other local checks

(Table 1). In the hill regions of Uttar Pradesh, it yielded 65% higher than standard variety K39 and 67% higher than local check Thapachini. It has medium slender grains.

Pant Dhan 6 has shown resistance

to leaf blast and brown leaf spot and moderate resistance to neck blast and leaf scald, the most common diseases in the hills. It has shown resistance to stem borer and moderate susceptibility to leafhoppers (Table 2). □

Table 1. Grain yield and days to flowering of Pant Dhan 6 in Uniform Variety Trials at Hawalbagh, Almora (U.P.), India, 1983-85.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				Days to 50% flowering			
	1983	1984	1985	Mean	1983	1984	1985	Mean
Pant Dhan 6	2.9 ^a	4.2 ^a	5.2 ^a	4.1	91	81	92	88
K39	1.4	2.1	4.0	2.5	79	73	83	78
Thapachini (local check)	2.0	3.5	3.6	2.4	98	107	102	102
CD at 0.05	1162	1164	824					
CV (%)	22.5	24.5	11.6					

^aSignificantly superior to K39 and Thapachini.

Table 2. Reaction of 3 varieties to diseases and insects at Hawalbagh, Almora, India, 1983 kharif.

Variety	Reaction ^a					
	Disease				Insect	
	Neck blast	Leaf scald	Sheath rot	Brown leaf spot	Stem borer	Leafhopper
Pant Dhan 6	5	5	7	3	3	7
K39	9	5	5	3	7	7
Thapachini (local check)	5	7	7	4	5	7

^aStandard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

Swarnaprabha, a physiologically efficient variety

Ch. Narasingarao and K.S. Murty, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India

Ptb 43 or Swarnaprabha, an early high-yielding variety from the cross Bhavani/Triveni was released in Kerala State in Feb 1985. The new variety is suitable for all three growing seasons.

Swarnaprabha and 11 other promising early rice cultivars of similar duration (Ratna as check) were field tested in 2 dry (Dec-Apr 1985 and 1986) and 1 wet (Jun-Nov 1985) season trials at 15- × 10-cm spacing. Sixty kg N as urea was applied in 3 equal splits: at seeding, 20 d after seeding, and booting.

Agronomic characteristics of Swarnaprabha and check variety Ratna at Cuttack, India.

Character	1985 wet season		1985 dry season		1986 dry season	
	Swarnaprabha	Ratna	Swarnaprabha	Ratna	Swarnaprabha	Ratna
Duration (d)	117	122	130	135	130	135
Height (cm)	113	86	107	82	112	86
Panicles/m ²	313	370	387	478	389	430
Spikelets/m ² × 10 ³	27.4	22.1	28.5	25.1	33.9	30.2
Grains/m ² × 10 ³	21.1	15.8	23.1	18.9	26.8	24.5
1,000-grain weight (g)	24.5	21.7	23.7	19.8	25.2	21.8
Total dry matter (g/m ²)	1012	786	1218	967	1159	999
Grain yield (g/m ²)	465	325	499	409	644	531
Harvest index	46	41	41	42	56	53
Solar energy utilization (Eu %)	1.11	0.91	1.00	0.75	0.94	0.75
Crop growth rate (panicle initiation to flowering, g/m ² per d)	19.9	12.2	23.1	12.0	19.2	18.8
Crop growth rate (flowering to harvest, g/m ² per d)	10.7	9.9	18.3	18.0	12.5	6.5
Sink capacity (g/m ²)	671	480	678	497	855	659
Postflowering dry matter (g/m ²)	363	248	493	449	400	215

Duration was 120 d in the wet season and 130 d in the dry (see table).

Productive panicles/ m² were about 390 in the dry season and 310 in the